

**THE PECULIARITIES OF TEACHING PROFESSIONAL
ENGLISH VOCABULARY TO THE STUDENTS OF LAW
UNIVERSITIES (BASED ON THE LEXEMES
«RIGHT» AND «LAW»)**

**Esanova Lutfiya Shermamat qizi¹, Buriyeva Muhayyo²,
Akhmedov Namoz³**

¹ Student of Termez State University ² Teacher at military lyceum in
Termez ³ Master's student at Termez State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6603555>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th May 2022

Accepted: 14th May 2022

Online: 31th May 2022

KEY WORDS

*lexemes «right» and
«law», teaching
professional vocabulary,
electronic resources,
legal terms.*

ABSTRACT

The article deals with the issues related to the efficiency of mastering students' professional vocabulary, provides possible translations of the lexeme «law» from Uzbek into English depending on the context, collocations with the words «right» and «law» in Uzbek and English equivalents. A brief overview of electronic resources that can be used by teachers and students of law schools and faculties in the translation of legal texts is given

The study of a foreign language in a non-linguistic university is aimed primarily at mastering professional vocabulary in a foreign language by students in order to be able to communicate with foreign colleagues on professional topics in the near future. As Professor E.A.Sorokina, «a language for special purposes belonging to a certain professional field is both a means of fixing scientific achievements and a means of learning, a means of obtaining professional knowledge and special skills» [5, p. 169].

RESEARCH BACKGROUND

However, mastering a foreign language at a professional level is a process that is not only time-consuming, but also time-consuming. Moreover, this process is complicated by the fact that undergraduate

students have only four years at their disposal. In this regard, many teachers and researchers emphasize the need to include elements of a professional orientation in the study of a foreign language from the very beginning of undergraduate studies. Therefore, N.Yu.Severova, emphasizing the need for early language professionalization, notes: «If earlier in the specialty for the first two years students studied the general language without taking into account specialization, and the remaining three years were devoted to the professionally oriented study of a foreign language, now, when after the bachelor's degree, graduates may need to find employment, under such a system, only two years remain for professionally oriented language learning. In this regard, there is an urgent need to

include elements of a professional orientation in the study of a foreign language as early as possible. Only such an approach can ensure high-quality training of a graduate» [3, p. 291].

For advanced students, the Oxford online dictionary website can be extremely helpful. Here you can find the interpretation of the English words «right», «law» and other English equivalents of the Russian word «right» in English, synonyms, as well as the etymology of these words and the approximate time of their fixation in the language.

In addition to dictionaries on the Internet, sites offering thematic online courses in English are a very effective electronic resource for learning professional vocabulary. One of the most striking examples of such an educational Internet resource is the site futurelearn.com. The courses are developed by leading universities in the UK, Australia and other countries where English is the state language or not, but is actively used in the social and business sphere (mainly universities in Europe and Southeast Asia). Among the large list of online courses on this site, using the search for the keywords «right» and «law», we find, for example, the following courses, both in the history and theory of law, and in individual legal branches, considering specific legal and philosophical and legal issues: Beyond the Ballot: Women's Rights and Suffrage from 1866 to Today (Royal Holloway, University of London), Environmental Justice (University of East Anglia), Law for Non-Lawyers: Introduction to Law (Monash University) Law for Non-Lawyers: Introduction to Law (Monash University), The Right to Education: Breaking Down the

Barriers (University of Glasgow) Corporate Law Professionals: Ethics, Regulation and Purpose (University of Birmingham), From Crime to Punishment: an Introduction to Criminal Justice (University of York).

DATA AND ANALYSIS

Information and communication technologies can provide great assistance in mastering the language at a professional level. In the modern world, electronic resources play an important role in the education of students. They are not the only source of information, but they are certainly a great addition to traditional teaching media such as print media.

In the process of teaching students of law faculties a foreign language for special purposes, the use of electronic information resources, in particular, thematic Internet sites, Internet versions of electronic dictionaries and encyclopedias, educational Internet portals that provide distance learning courses, provides fairly high results in the development of professional vocabulary.

One of the advantages of electronic dictionaries over traditional ones is the possibility of their constant editing and replenishment. As Yu.E.Dorokhova, «the actual practice of translation shows that often the translator does not find in a bilingual dictionary such a translation option that satisfies the conditions of a particular context. This may be due both to differences in the functioning of language systems, and to the imperfection of dictionaries» [1, p. 74]. This «imperfection» is successfully eliminated in electronic dictionaries, and not only developers, but also registered users replenish the collection of words, phrases and examples from texts.

With all the variety of electronic online dictionaries, ABBYY Lingvo dictionaries obviously occupy a leading position. This collection of dictionaries makes it possible not only in a matter of seconds to find the translation of the desired word, for example, a legal term, but also provides a large number of phrases with the desired term and excerpts from texts, which allows you to see in what context this term can be used. Thus, having received the task to find a dictionary translation of the lexeme «right», on the site lingvolive.com the student will find the following information: English correspondences, the main ones of which are the words «right» and «law», stable phrases with the Uzbek word including terms-phrases, and their translation into English, which in most cases is not literal. For example, «vote, suffrage, franchise – saylov huquqi», «criminal law – jinoyat kodeksi», «serfdom (historical) – krepostnoy huquqi», «study law – bilim olish huquqi», «adjective law – protsessual huquq», «adjective patent law – intellektual mulk huquqi». I would especially like to note the educational dictionary available in the arsenal of this site, since it gives an interpretation of the English words «right» and «law» in Russian, which greatly facilitates the process of studying legal vocabulary for first-year students of law schools and faculties: «a set of social norms and the science of them» (law); «right to claim» (claim), «freedom to do smth.» (right) [7].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An increasingly important role in the learning process in the modern world is played by such a type of electronic resource as an electronic educational environment (ELE), which is an Internet platform that

can be filled with various educational materials at your discretion, depending on the learning goals and current tasks. Usually, the teacher independently or with the help of technical staff forms the structure of the electronic educational environment, but modern pedagogy of cooperation, considering education as a two-way process, calls for the involvement of students as full participants in it. Thus, the teacher can also instruct his students to replenish the EOS with new materials. As N.Yu.Severova notes, teachers should trust students more in terms of forming the content of the electronic educational environment: «In teaching foreign languages, such work can be very, very effective. In the course of search activities, students learn to work with authentic information in a foreign language, simultaneously getting acquainted with new vocabulary and ways of expressing thoughts» [4]. This type of assignment is extremely useful for students, future professionals in their field, because in the process of performing they acquire additional, professionally significant competencies.

As a project activity, for example, students can be entrusted with the formation of glossaries on certain legal topics, such as thematic search for stable phrases of legal vocabulary: «Basic terms of environmental law», «Terms related to law and judicial administration», etc. As a result, all the material accumulated by the students of the group or course becomes available to each of them and the teachers and can be successfully used in the future for in-depth study and preparation for exams, not only in the group that completed the project, but by other students in this direction.

CONCLUSION

Modern electronic resources for learning foreign languages are quite diverse and are constantly being improved. A significant contribution to their change and

improvement is made by both teachers and students who constantly use these resources for cognitive, educational and professional purposes.

References:

1. Dorokhova Yu.E. Bilingual lexicography and translation // Language as a system and activity - 4. Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference dedicated to the 95th anniversary of the birth of Lyudmila Alekseevna Vvedenskaya. Rostov-on-Don: Foundation, 2013, pp. 73-78.
2. Kubits G.V. Professionalization of linguistic personality: On the example of legal discourse: dis. ... cand. philologist. Sciences. Chelyabinsk, 2005. 258 p.
3. Severova N.Yu. Introduction of elements of professionalization into the practice of teaching a foreign language at the initial stage of undergraduate studies in order to ensure the quality of graduate training (on the example of the German language, a non-linguistic university) // Quality education: problems and prospects (collection of scientific articles). M.: MGPU, 2016. S. 289-298.
4. Severova N.Yu. Virtual educational environment: the problem of content // Creation of a virtual intercultural educational space by means of e-learning technologies. Digest of articles. M.: MGPU, 2017. S. 197-202.
5. Sorokina E.A. Language for specific purposes as a means of communication. // Bulletin of the Chelyabinsk State University. Number: 4 (386). 2016. S. 169-172.
6. URL: <https://www.futurelearn.com/> [Electronic resource], date of access: 04/15/2018.
7. URL: <https://www.lingvolive.com/ru-ru> [Electronic resource], date of access: 04/15/2018.
8. URL: <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/> [Electronic resource], date of access: 04/15/2018.
9. URL: <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com> [Electronic resource], accessed 04/15/2018.